

Toward measuring the usability of decision support applications in fog computing environment

Oras Abdulkhudhur Hussein, Ayad Hameed Mousa

Department of Computer Science, College of Computer Science and Information Technology, University of Kerbala
Karbala, Iraq

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jun 27, 2022

Revised Jan 10, 2023

Accepted Jan 14, 2023

Keywords:

Decision support systems
application

Decision support systems
usability

Fog computing environment
usability

Pilot study

Software usability

ABSTRACT

Decision support systems are applications that provide meaningful information and help with decision support. To gain the benefits of these applications, they need to be used optimally. Thus, the optimal manner to utilize relies on several properties, such as usability. This research aims to investigate the decision support systems applications (DSS) in terms of usability evaluation and propose a usability instrument for DSS in a fog computing environment. Recently, complexity is a major problem with most software products. Hence, the way to ensure user satisfaction is by measuring its usability. The study is based on the research question: What dimensions and their elements that utilize to evaluate the usability of DSS applications. A systematic literature review (SLR) was conducted to understand and extract all the instrument's dimensions and elements. To confirm the validity of the proposed instrument, multi scientific methods were adapted such as face validity, a pilot study for testing the goodness of proposed instrument consistency, and factor analysis. Furthermore, Bartlett's test was utilized to ensure the reliability of the developed instrument. Eventually, the validated instrument was used to evaluate DSS application in a fog computing environment. The findings show that the proposed instrument is workable in practice.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Ayad Hameed Mousa

Department of Computer Science, College of Computer Science and Information Technology

University of Kerbala

239 Freaha Road, Karbala, Iraq

Email: ayad.h@uokerbala.edu.iq

1. INTRODUCTION

The decision-making process is an inherently human activity that can have worthy impacts [1], [2]. It is probably not surprising that researchers have tried to improve the goodness of decisions by utilizing computer technologies to increase and extend human capabilities [3]. Decision support systems (DSS) is a form of software system that can provide aid to organizations to tackle vital heterogeneous and multi-sources data and transform it into useful information. DSS also performs analysis and several data management processes and represents one of the main areas of information systems. The context of the study is a decision support system in a fog computing environment where the primary actor is a DSS staff involved in providing decision support on DSS applications. The DSS staff became very aware of the DSS usability problems and also of a deficiency of a DSS usability evaluation process [4].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Decision support systems

In recent decades, with the emergence of big data for the abundance of data, it is abundantly clear that most decisions are based on data. Data is a backbone for decision support systems. In the same aspect, decision support systems target to support decision-makers in making the right decisions at the right time [5],[6].

2.2. Software testing in DSS applications

According to [7], usability testing is to answer whether the system satisfies the user requirement and needs. In the same aspect, usability can be defined as the extent to which a software product can be easily adopted and used by users to achieve specific goals efficiently and effectively. Besides, Nilson and Cameron [8] states that the process of usability assessment of software incorporates three principal goals; i) to what extent the user can easily access and use the system's functions, ii) to measure the experience of users interacting with this system, and iii) to determine if there are any particular problems using this system [7].

2.3. Usability in DSS applications

DSS usability can be considered a significant factor in DSS application for determining the best of it. DSS aims to help and support the massive and heterogeneous data sources and flow of relevant data by determining and handling the information into meaningful information [9]. Besides, to gain from the actual users about the DSS usability and according to [10], usability testing for DSS applications should be conducted. According to the institute of medicine, heightening the usability of DSS applications leads to reducing errors and making better decisions [11], [12].

3. USABILITY MEASUREMENT

According to [13], [14], identifying the usability metrics is easier than collecting them. Often, usability is measured based on users' satisfaction with a given application. Usability measures are based on the extent to which the functional and non-functional requirements are met for the intended application. Accordingly, proposing and developing a usability test instrument will also depend on the extent to which the services for this application are met for user needs, and of course, according to the nature of the intended application [15]. As it is evident that the applications have become customized and each application is designed and developed to solve a specific problem or for pre-defined purposes, so the usability test for this application also depends on the main purpose of this application. Accordingly, and in the context of this study, the proposed instrument for measuring the usability of DSS applications will focus on five important dimensions [1]. Besides, usability testing focuses on the actual's users' experience with the intended application, as well as their comments and feedback during the use of the such application in their environments [13].

4. INSTRUMENT DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT

To measure users' experience towards measuring usability for DSS applications. In this study, the questionnaire as an evaluation instrument for DSS applications has been used for its reliability and wide adoption [16], [17]. To meet the study objectives, the questionnaire based-instrument is designed to elicit comments, suggestions, and feedback regarding DSS usability, and is named (QU-DSS). Since the proposed instrument (DU-DSS) has concerned to usability of DSS, the QU-DSS usability dimensions and their items has identified through systematic literature review (SLR). Figure 1 depicted the SLR protocol.

Figure 1. SLR protocol

According to [18], argue that adapted a systematic approach is a significant in developing evaluation instrument. Figure 2 presents the main phases of the evaluation instrument design. As indicated from Figure 2, the designing procedure of the QU-DSS start with SLR to identify the instrument dimensions and their items. Consequently, the findings of SLR depict that the QU-DSS evaluation instrument have five dimensions named: usefulness, simplicity, reliability, flexibility, and decision-support. Several standard instruments such as questionnaire for user interface satisfaction (QUIS) by Chin *et al.* [19], perceived usefulness and ease of use (PUEU) by Davis [20], software usability measurement inventory (SUMI) by Kirakowski *et al.* [21], and practical heuristics for usability evaluation (PHUE) by Chung and Sahari [22] were widely adapted widely adapted and they have similar dimensions; therefore, most of the relevant dimensions' items have adapted and utilized and later the first draft of QU-DSS was released.

As indicated in Table 1, The proposed instrument had formed a sequence of items (questions) with a suitable answer for each question. Accordingly, the QU-DSS instrument was utilized to measure the usefulness, simplicity, flexibility, reliability, as well as decision support under usability for DSS applications based on a fog computing environment.

Figure 2. Evaluation instrument design (main phases)

Table 1. The proposed instrument (first draft)

No	QU-DSS dimensions	QU-DSS items	Author and year
1	Usefulness (UFL) 7 items	QU-DSS-UFL-1 QU-DSS-UFL-2 QU-DSS-UFL-3 QU-DSS-UFL-4 QU-DSS-UFL-5 QU-DSS-UFL-6 QU-DSS-UFL-7	[23], [24] and proposed by the researcher
2	Simplicity (SMP) 6 items	QU-DSS-SMP-1 QU-DSS-SMP-2 QU-DSS-SMP-3 QU-DSS-SMP-4 QU-DSS-SMP-5 QU-DSS-SMP-6	[25], [26] and proposed by the researcher
3	Reliability (REL) 7 items	QU-DSS-REL-1 QU-DSS-REL-2 QU-DSS-REL-3 QU-DSS-REL-4 QU-DSS-REL-5 QU-DSS-REL-6 QU-DSS-REL-7	[24], [27], [28] and proposed by the researcher
4	decision support (DS) 7 items	QU-DSS-DS-1 QU-DSS-DS-2 QU-DSS-DS-3 QU-DSS-DS-4 QU-DSS-DS-5 QU-DSS-DS-6 QU-DSS-DS-7	[9], [29], [30] and proposed by the researcher
5	Flexibility (FLX) 6 items	QU-DSS-FLX-1 QU-DSS-FLX-2 QU-DSS-FLX-3 QU-DSS-FLX-4 QU-DSS-FLX-5 QU-DSS-FLX-6	[31]–[35] and proposed by the researcher

The QU-DSS was piloted to measure its reliability and validity before deliver it to in real environment in measuring DSS application based on fog computing environment. Besides, [36] in this study, researchers used “somewhat agree” instead of the “neutral” option to force respondents to choose a side. Thus, a 5-point likert-type scale has been utilized in the research, and the interpretations of the scales: strongly agree; agree; somewhat agree; disagree, and strongly disagree.

5. PILOT TEST: MEASURING INSTRUMENT GOODNESS

To evaluate the whole QU-DSS instrument under survey conditions. A pilot study was conducted. By pilot testing, the instrument's problems are determined before utilizing the full examination. Pilot testing focuses on each question in the proposed instrument and exam the validity. It checks whether the item is interpreting and representing the information it's intended to measure [37], [38].

5.1. Subject selection

In the context of this study, the pilot test conducted with 84 respondents was obtained among the college of computer science postgraduate students as well as CS lecturers. The respondent number is enough to achieve reliable findings in the statistical test, as supported by [39]–[41]. The total number of sample participants was 84. The pilot test data showed 50 females (59%) and 34 males (41%). Most of the participants revealed their age to be above 30.

5.2. QU-DSS validation

In the context of this study, two well-known methods were adopted to validate QU-DSS instrument, the first one is content validity while the second one is interitem consistency analysis. for content validity, face validity was utilized as supported by [42]. The justification for conducting face validity to confirm that the QU-DSS proposed instrument includes an adequate set of measuring elements of the intended dimension. Accordingly, this study employed seven experts face-to-face and through e-mail to review the QU-DSS items in terms of validity of the content. The review finding of the experts indicates that some QU-DSS items were not suitable sufficiently to use and did not meet well with the intended QU-DSS dimensions. Consequently, QU-DSS's first draft was modified in terms of repositioning, rewording, and sometimes discarding some irrelevant items. To confirm consistency, the reliability test was conducted as a second method for QU-DSS instrument. Thus, consistency is measured by the reliability test. The Cronbach's coefficient alpha (α) was counted [43], [44]. This study conducted α test and considered ($\alpha > 0.6$) to be significant, as supported by [45]. Table 2 depict the findings of the reliability test of the QU-DSS measurement items, the findings indicate that QU-DSS instrument are consistent and significant, and can be adapted to utilize for measuring the usability and decision support for DSS application in for computing environment.

Table 2. Finding of measuring reliability

No	QU-DSS dimensions	No. of items	Cronbach's alpha
1	QU-DSS-UFL	7	0.783
2	QU-DSS-SMP	6	0.725
3	QU-DSS-REL	7	0.714
4	QU-DSS-DS	7	0.791
5	QU-DSS-FLX	6	0.708

5.3. Factor analysis process

To confirm the degree of significance of QU-DSS items, factor analysis was conducted. The accepting items are selected based on Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test, and the value of factor loading [44], [46], [47]. Consequently, to organize the data for factor loading, KMO test was conducted. As indicated in Table 3, the obtained findings of KMO test have accepted based on the condition of KMO test ≥ 0.50 .

Table 3. The KMO overall findings

No	QU-DSS dimensions	No. of items	KMO	The value of Bartlett's test
1	QU-DSS-UFL	7	0.783	0.000
2	QU-DSS-SMP	6	0.725	0.000
3	QU-DSS-REL	7	0.714	0.000
4	QU-DSS-DS	7	0.791	0.000
5	QU-DSS-FLX	6	0.708	0.000

As indicated from Table 3 the Bartlett’s test of sphericity value is 0.000 for all dimensions, this indicates that the second condition is met ($p \leq 0.05$). Thence, this motivates that the data are willing and able for factor loading analysis test. Table 4 detailed the factor loading test. As can be seen in Table 4, all items in QU-DSS are usable and represent the respective dimensions except the three items marked with an asterisk (*) are excluded from the test and whose factor loading values are less than 0.50 as supported by [48].

Table 4. The factor loading overall findings

No	QU-DSS dimensions	QU-DSS items	Factor loading value
1	Usefulness (ufl) 7 items	QU-DSS-UFL-1	0.587
		QU-DSS-UFL-2	0.661
		QU-DSS-UFL-3	0.625
		QU-DSS-UFL-4	0.554
		QU-DSS-UFL-5	0.362*
		QU-DSS-UFL-6	0.511
		QU-DSS-UFL-7	0.531
2	Simplicity (smp) 6 items	QU-DSS-SMP-1	0.686
		QU-DSS-SMP-2	0.534
		QU-DSS-SMP-3	0.541
		QU-DSS-SMP-4	0.661
		QU-DSS-SMP-5	0.672
		QU-DSS-SMP-6	0.572
3	Reliability (REL) 7 items	QU-DSS-REL-1	0.645
		QU-DSS-REL-2	0.387*
		QU-DSS-REL-3	0.615
		QU-DSS-REL-4	0.609
		QU-DSS-REL-5	0.694
		QU-DSS-REL-6	0.621
		QU-DSS-REL-7	0.566
4	Decision support (DS) 7 items	QU-DSS-DS-1	0.551
		QU-DSS-DS-2	0.686
		QU-DSS-DS-3	0.538
		QU-DSS-DS-4	0.546
		QU-DSS-DS-5	0.665
		QU-DSS-DS-6	0.673
		QU-DSS-DS-7	0.578
5	Flexibility (FLX) 6 items	QU-DSS-FLX-1	0.689
		QU-DSS-FLX-2	0.534
		QU-DSS-FLX-3	0.545
		QU-DSS-FLX-4	0.662
		QU-DSS-FLX-5	0.373*
		QU-DSS-FLX-6	0.571

6. USE QU-DSS FOR USABILITY MEASUREMENT

After confirming the validity of the developed tool for use, it was used to measure the usability of a clinical decision support system developed previously by the researcher. The actual users of the system in three government hospitals (27 clinicians) as well as the sixth stage students belonging to the faculty of medicine (73) total (100), were asked to evaluate the developed system in terms of usability. Moreover, to sum up or to describe the characteristics of Selected data set or samples, the descriptive statistics was conducted (the mean (M) and standard deviation (STD) were calculated). Figures 3 to 8 and Tables 5 to 9 respectively show the results obtained for usefulness, simplicity, reliability, decision support, and flexibility through the evaluation process.

Table 5. Usefulness dimension findings

No	Usefulness items	STD	M	1	2	3	4	5
Frequency and percentage (%)								
1	QU-DSS-UFL1	1.023	4.541	0.0	0.0	3	80	17
2	QU-DSS-UFL2	1.045	4.672	0.0	0.0	4	78	18
3	QU-DSS-UFL3	1.101	4.826	0.0	0.0	2	80	18
4	QU-DSS-UFL4	1.087	4.911	0.0	0.0	3	80	17
5	QU-DSS-UFL5	1.102	4.541	0.0	0.0	4	78	18
6	QU-DSS-UFL6	1.031	4.441	0.0	0.0	2	80	18
Average						3	80	17

Note: 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 means :strongly disagree, disagree, somewhat agree, agree, strongly agree

Figure 3. Usefulness dimension findings

In terms of usefulness, the findings details are illustrated in Table 5 and Figure 3. The majority of participants are either strongly agree or agree and few of them are somewhat agree. Thus, the DSS application that measured by QU-DSS is useful.

Table 6. Simplicity dimension findings

No	Simplicity items	STD	M	1	2	3	4	5
				Frequency and percentage (%)				
1	QU-DSS-SMP1	1.103	4.740	0.0	0.0	7	77	16
2	QU-DSS-SMP2	1.145	4.274	0.0	0.0	5	74	18
3	QU-DSS-SMP3	1.055	4.427	0.0	0.0	7	76	17
4	QU-DSS-SMP4	1.387	4.713	0.0	0.0	7	77	16
5	QU-DSS-SMP5	1.215	4.642	0.0	0.0	5	74	18
6	QU-DSS-SMP6	1.065	4.148	0.0	0.0	7	76	17
				Average		7	77	16

Note: 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 means :strongly disagree, disagree, somewhat agree, agree, strongly agree

Figure 4. Simplicity dimension findings

In terms of simplicity, the findings details are illustrated in Table 5 and Figure 4. The majority of participants are either strongly agree or agree and few of them are somewhat agree. Thus, the DSS application that measured by QU-DSS has the characteristic of simplicity.

Table 7. Reliability dimension findings

No	Reliability items	STD	M	1	2	3	4	5
				Frequency and percentage (%)				
1	QU-DSS-REL1	1.103	4.740	0.0	0.0	15	50	35
2	QU-DSS-REL2	1.105	4.274	0.0	0.0	14	51	35
3	QU-DSS-REL3	1.005	4.427	0.0	0.0	16	49	35
4	QU-DSS-REL4	1.307	4.713	0.0	0.0	15	50	35
5	QU-DSS-REL5	1.205	4.642	0.0	0.0	14	51	35
6	QU-DSS-REL6	1.005	4.148	0.0	0.0	16	49	35
				Average		15	50	35

Note: 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 means :strongly disagree, disagree, somewhat agree, agree, strongly agree

Figure 5. Reliability dimension findings

In terms of reliability, the findings details are illustrated in Table 6 and Figure 5. The majority of participants are either strongly agree or agree and few of them are somewhat agree. Thus, the DSS application that measured by QU-DSS confirm are reliable.

Table 8. Decision-support dimension findings

No	Decision-support items	STD	M	Frequency and percentage (%)					
				1	2	3	4	5	
1	QU-DSS-DS1	1.001	4.942	0.0	0.0	10	65	25	
2	QU-DSS-DS2	1.504	4.775	0.0	0.0	9	67	24	
3	QU-DSS-DS3	1.115	4.827	0.0	0.0	11	66	23	
4	QU-DSS-DS4	1.117	4.419	0.0	0.0	10	65	25	
5	QU-DSS-DS5	1.212	4.547	0.0	0.0	9	67	24	
6	QU-DSS-DS6	1.106	4.348	0.0	0.0	11	66	23	
						Average	10	65	25

Note: 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 means :strongly disagree, disagree, somewhat agree, agree, strongly agree

Figure 6. Decision-support dimension findings

In terms of decision-support, the findings details are illustrated in Table 7 and Figure 6. The majority of participants are either strongly agree or agree and few of them are somewhat agree. Thus, the DSS application that measured by QU-DSS can support decision-making process.

Table 9. Flexibility dimension findings

No	Flexibility items	STD	M	Frequency and percentage (%)					
				1	2	3	4	5	
1	QU-DSS-FLX1	1.452	4.142	0.0	0.0	11	70	19	
2	QU-DSS-FLX2	1.511	4.275	0.0	0.0	10	72	18	
3	QU-DSS-FLX3	1.712	4.327	0.0	0.0	12	71	17	
4	QU-DSS-FLX4	1.602	4.479	0.0	0.0	11	70	19	
5	QU-DSS-FLX5	1.801	4.547	0.0	0.0	10	72	18	
6	QU-DSS-FLX6	1.105	4.168	0.0	0.0	12	71	17	
						Average	11	70	19

Note: 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 means :strongly disagree, disagree, somewhat agree, agree, strongly agree

Figure 7. Flexibility dimension findings

In terms of flexibility, the findings details are illustrated in Table 8 and Figure 7. The majority of participants are either strongly agree or agree and few of them are somewhat agree. Thus, the DSS application that measured by QU-DSS are flexible. In line with the above situation, the findings confirm that QU-DSS are usable in terms of flexibility, reliability, simplicity, usefulness, and decision-support. Figure 8 illustrate the overall usability test findings.

Figure 8. The overall usability test findings

7. CONCLUSION

Decision support systems are very important systems in most organizations, accordingly designing high-quality systems in terms of ease of use and decision support is required. The design and development of usability assessment tools is one of the necessities that must be available for all types of applications, especially decision support systems. Whenever the developed tool is reliable and designed in an organized and systematic way, the results of the evaluation are reliable and reliable.

In this paper, an assessment tool for decision support systems was designed and developed to measure the ease of use of decision support systems. This tool consists of five dimensions (usefulness), each dimension has own items. After completing the development of the QU-DSS, it was used to evaluate the clinical decision support system previously developed by the researcher. The obtained results showed that the QU-DSS is valid and usable in evaluating decision support systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the fruitful work and patience demonstrated by the expert members during the validation process of the proposed instrument. In addition, the authors acknowledge and thank the University of Kerbala and the College of Computer Science and Information Technology for their endless support and cooperation in making this research effort true.

REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Zhou, Z. Yin, Q. Ying, and S. Wang, "Intelligent data mining and decision system for commercial decision making," *TELKOMNIKA Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 792–801, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.11591/telkomnika.v12i1.3977.
- [2] S. Kumar, D. S. Sathyadevi, and G. Sivanesh, "Decision support system for medical diagnosis using data mining," *International Journal of Computer Science Issues (IJCSI)*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 147–153, 2011.
- [3] O. AlShorman, B. AlShorman, M. Al-khassaweneh, and F. Alkahtani, "A review of internet of medical things (IoMT) - based remote health monitoring through wearable sensors: a case study for diabetic patients," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 414–422, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v20.i1.pp414-422.
- [4] E. Walling and C. Vaneeckhaute, "Developing successful environmental decision support systems: challenges and best practices," *Journal of Environmental Management*, vol. 264, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110513.
- [5] R. H. Bonczek, C. W. Holsapple, and A. B. Whinston, *Foundations of decision support systems*. Elsevier, 1981.
- [6] K. Cresswell, M. Callaghan, S. Khan, Z. Sheikh, H. Mozaffar, and A. Sheikh, "Investigating the use of data-driven artificial intelligence in computerised decision support systems for health and social care: a systematic review," *Health Informatics Journal*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 2138–2147, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1177/1460458219900452.
- [7] K. Hornbæk, "Current practice in measuring usability: challenges to usability studies and research," *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, vol. 64, no. 2, pp. 79–102, Feb. 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhcs.2005.06.002.
- [8] T. Nilson and P. J. Cameron, "Triple arrays from difference sets," *Journal of Combinatorial Designs*, vol. 25, no. 11, pp. 494–506, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.1002/jcd.21569.
- [9] B. Knols, M. Louws, A. Hardenbol, J. Dehmeshki, and M. Askari, "The usability aspects of medication-related decision support systems in the inpatient setting: a systematic review," *Health Informatics Journal*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 613–627, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1177/1460458219841167.
- [10] C. Jaja, J. Pares-Avila, S. Wolpin, and D. Berry, "Usability evaluation of the interactive personal patient profile-prostate decision support system with African American men," *Journal of the National Medical Association*, vol. 102, no. 4, pp. 290–302, Apr. 2010, doi: 10.1016/S0027-9684(15)30601-5.
- [11] H. L. Farley *et al.*, "Quality and safety implications of emergency department information systems," *Annals of Emergency Medicine*, vol. 62, no. 4, pp. 399–407, Oct. 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.annemergmed.2013.05.019.
- [12] F. Thum *et al.*, "Usability improvement of a clinical decision support system," in *DUXU 2014: Design, User Experience, and Usability. User Experience Design for Everyday Life Applications and Services*, Cham: Springer, 2014, pp. 125–131, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-07635-5_13.
- [13] N. S. Aziz, N. S. Sulaiman, W. N. I. T. M. Hassan, N. L. Zakaria, and A. Yaacob, "A review of website measurement for website usability evaluation," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1874, no. 1, May 2021, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1874/1/012045.
- [14] Z. T. Al-Ars and A. Al-Bakry, "A web/mobile decision support system to improve medical diagnosis using a combination of K-Mean and fuzzy logic," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control)*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 3145–3154, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.12928/telkomnika.v17i6.12715.
- [15] D. L. Berry *et al.*, "Development and evaluation of the personal patient profile-prostate (P3P), a web-based decision support system for men newly diagnosed with localized prostate cancer," *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, Dec. 2010, doi: 10.2196/jmir.1576.
- [16] R. Allvin, E. Svensson, N. Rawal, M. Ehnfors, A.-M. Kling, and E. Idvall, "The postoperative recovery profile (PRP) - a multidimensional questionnaire for evaluation of recovery profiles," *Journal of Evaluation in Clinical Practice*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 236–243, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2753.2010.01428.x.
- [17] P. Lietz, "Research into questionnaire design: a summary of the literature," *International Journal of Market Research*, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 249–272, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.2501/S147078530920120X.
- [18] S. Thillaiampalam, T. Okamura, and F. Nakamura, "A systematic approach for questionnaire design on new transit system implementation in developing countries," *Journal of the Eastern Asia Society for Transportation Studies*, vol. 7, pp. 1664–1679, 2007, doi: 10.11175/easts.7.1664.
- [19] J. P. Chin, V. A. Diehl, and L. K. Norman, "Development of an instrument measuring user satisfaction of the human-computer interface," in *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems - CHI '88*, 1988, pp. 213–218, doi: 10.1145/57167.57203.
- [20] F. D. Davis, "Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology," *MIS Quarterly*, vol. 13, no. 3, Sep. 1989, doi: 10.2307/249008.
- [21] J. Kirakowski and M. Corbett, "SUMI: the software usability measurement inventory," *British Journal of Educational Technology*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 210–212, Sep. 1993, doi: 10.1111/j.1467-8535.1993.tb00076.x.
- [22] C. T. Kun and N. Sahari, "Utilitarian or experiential? an analysis of usability questionnaires," *International Journal of Computer Theory and Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 167–171, Apr. 2015, doi: 10.7763/IJCTE.2015.V7.950.
- [23] G. Tsakonas and C. Papatheodorou, "Analysing and evaluating usefulness and usability in electronic information services," *Journal of Information Science*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 400–419, Oct. 2006, doi: 10.1177/0165551506065934.
- [24] B. Parmanto, A. N. L. Jr., K. M. Graham, and M. H. Bertolet, "Development of the telehealth usability questionnaire (TUQ)," *International Journal of Telerehabilitation*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 3–10, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.5195/ijt.2016.6196.
- [25] A. Chu *et al.*, "Usability of learning moment: features of an e-learning tool that maximize adoption by students," *Western Journal of Emergency Medicine*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 78–84, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.5811/westjem.2019.6.42657.
- [26] D. Lee, J. Moon, Y. J. Kim, and M. Y. Yi, "Antecedents and consequences of mobile phone usability: linking simplicity and interactivity to satisfaction, trust, and brand loyalty," *Information & Management*, vol. 52, no. 3, pp. 295–304, Apr. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.im.2014.12.001.
- [27] Y. S. Ryu and T. L. Smith-Jackson, "Reliability and validity of the mobile phone usability questionnaire (MPUQ)," *Journal of Usability Studies*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 39–53, 2006.
- [28] O. Erdiņ and J. R. Lewis, "Psychometric evaluation of the T-CSUQ: the Turkish version of the computer system usability questionnaire," *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 319–326, Apr. 2013, doi: 10.1080/10447318.2012.711702.
- [29] E. R. Melnick *et al.*, "Patient-centered decision support: formative usability evaluation of integrated clinical decision support with a patient decision aid for minor head injury in the emergency department," *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, vol. 19, no. 5, May 2017, doi: 10.2196/jmir.7846.
- [30] T. Feghali, I. Zbib, and S. Hallal, "A web-based decision support tool for academic advising," *Educational Technology and Society*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 82–94, 2011.

- [31] P. Nokelainen, "An empirical assessment of pedagogical usability criteria for digital learning material with elementary school students," *Educational Technology and Society*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 178–197, 2006.
- [32] M. A. Storey, B. Phillips, M. Maczewski, and M. Wang, "Evaluating the usability of web-based learning tools," *Educational Technology and Society*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 91–100, 2002.
- [33] G. M. Kituyi and H. Anjoga, "Improvement of e-government service usability in developing countries: empirical experiences of Uganda," *Journal of Emerging Trends in Computing and Information Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 3, 2013.
- [34] N. Nordin, E. Zakaria, N. R. N. Mohamed, and M. A. Embi, "Pedagogical usability of the geometer's sketchpad (GSP) digital module in the mathematics teaching," *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 113–117, 2010.
- [35] A. Hinderks, D. Winter, M. Schrepp, and J. Thomaschewski, "Applicability of user experience and usability questionnaires," *Journal of Universal Computer Science*, vol. 25, no. 13, pp. 1717–1735, 2019.
- [36] J. Schreiber and K. Asner-Self, *Educational research : the interrelationship of questions, sampling, design, and analysis*. Hoboken: Wiley, 2011.
- [37] A. Shanmugam, F. Z. Abidin, and H. Tolos, "Reliability test on factors influencing retirement confidence among working adults in Malaysia: a pilot study," *Asian Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities*, vol. 7, no. May, pp. 1–8, 2018.
- [38] I. Ahmad and S. Ahmad, "Multiple skills and medium enterprises' performance in Punjab Pakistan: a pilot study," *The Journal of Social Sciences Research*, vol. 2018, no. SPI4, pp. 44–49, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.32861/jssr.spi4.44.49.
- [39] S. Ueno and U. Sekaran, "The influence of culture on budget control practices in the USA and Japan: An empirical study," *Journal of International Business Studies*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 659–674, 1992, doi: 10.1057/palgrave.jibs.8490282.
- [40] U. Sekaran and R. Bougie, *Research methods for business: a skill building approach*, 7th ed. John Wiley & Sons, 2016, pp. 1-448.
- [41] S. Mann, "Research methods for business: a skill-building approach," *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, vol. 34, no. 7, pp. 700–701, Sep. 2013, doi: 10.1108/LODJ-06-2013-0079.
- [42] K. A. M. Khidzir, N. Z. Ismail, and A. R. Abdullah, "Validity and reliability of instrument to measure social media skills among small and medium entrepreneurs at Pengkalan Datu River," *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1026–1037, 2018.
- [43] S. Bajpai and R. Bajpai, "Goodness of measurement: reliability and validity," *International Journal of Medical Science and Public Health*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 112–115, 2013.
- [44] K. L. Barton, W. L. Wrieden, and A. S. Anderson, "Validity and reliability of a short questionnaire for assessing the impact of cooking skills interventions," *Journal of Human Nutrition and Dietetics*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 588–595, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1111/j.1365-277X.2011.01180.x.
- [45] S. Z. S. Tabish and K. N. Jha, "Success traits for a construction project," *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, vol. 138, no. 10, pp. 1131–1138, Oct. 2012, doi: 10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0000538.
- [46] R. A. Fox, I. C. McManus, and B. C. Winder, "The shortened study process questionnaire: an investigation of its structure and longitudinal stability using confirmatory factor analysis," *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 511–530, Dec. 2001, doi: 10.1348/000709901158659.
- [47] H. Kang, "A guide on the use of factor analysis in the assessment of construct validity," *Journal of Korean Academy of Nursing*, vol. 43, no. 5, pp. 587–594, 2013, doi: 10.4040/jkan.2013.43.5.587.
- [48] T. Rajalahti and O. M. Kvalheim, "Multivariate data analysis in pharmaceuticals: a tutorial review," *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, vol. 417, no. 1–2, pp. 280–290, Sep. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2011.02.019.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Oras Abdulkhudhur Hussein was born in Karbala in 1985. She got BSc in computer science from the University of Kerbala in 2007. She is ongoing now final step MSc degree in computer science. Interesting in data science in the fog computing environment and software engineering. She works in the Ministry of education as a computer teacher since 2008 and is ongoing. She can be contacted at oras.a@s.uokerbala.edu.iq.

Ayad Hameed Mousa received his Ph.D. in computer science in 2017 and is an assistant professor at the College of Computer Science and Information Technology, University of Kerbala, Department of Computer Science. His research is situated in the field of technology and innovation, with a special focus on software engineering, business intelligence modeling, data mining, data warehouse, and e-learning modeling. He is actively engaged in several scientific projects (bilateral cooperation, national projects). A university lecturer from 2005 and ongoing. He is the author or co-author of more than 34 papers in international journals and international conference contributions. He can be contacted at email: ayad.h@uokerbala.edu.iq.